

Definitions of Plantar Pressure Representations

Notations

In the mathematical definitions below, we will employ the following notations:

- A pixel is a spatial location defined by the coordinates (x, y) where x is a position along the anterior-posterior axis, and y is a position along the medial-lateral axis.
- A fixed time point is defined by the variable t .
- A frame of a plantar pressure measurement is defined to be a two-dimensional image $f_t(x, y)$ containing all the plantar pressures sampled at the time point t . A frame is also a function parameterized by a pixel: when provided a pixel, a frame can return the plantar pressure measured at the corresponding spatial location.
- A full dynamic plantar pressure measurement is a video $V(x, y, t)$ and is also a three-dimensional function parameterized by a pixel and a time point. Given a pixel and time point, a plantar pressure measurement can return the plantar pressure measured at the given spatial location and time point.
- A plantar pressure measurement V is also equally defined as a sequence of frames $V = \{f_0, \dots, f_T\}$ collected from the beginning of the measurement ($t = 0$) to the end ($t = T$).
- A region of Interest R is defined as a set of contiguous pixels, $R = \{(x_0, y_0), \dots, (x_k, y_k)\}$, that describe an anatomical location on the plantar pressure measurement.

Region of Interest: Peak Pressure (ROI-PEAK)

The peak pressure of a region of interest $P_{peak}(R)$ is defined to be the maximum pressure response over all pixels in the region R , and over all time points in the plantar pressure measurement:

$$P_{peak}(R) = \max_{(x,y) \in R} \max_t V(x, y, t) \quad (1)$$

Region of Interest: Mean Pressure (ROI-MEAN)

The mean pressure of a region of interest $P_{mean}(R)$ is defined to be the average pressure response over all pixels in the region R over all time points:

$$P_{mean}(R) = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_{(x,y) \in R} \sum_{t=0}^T V(x, y, t) \quad (2)$$

In the above equation, the normalization constant Z is defined to be the number of non-zero plantar pressures recorded in the region of interest across all time points:

$$Z = \sum_{(x,y) \in R} \sum_{t=0}^T -\delta [V(x,y,t)] + 1 \quad (3)$$

In the above equation, δ is the Dirac delta function.

Region of Interest: Pressure-Time Integral (ROI-PTI)

The pressure-time integral of a region of interest $P_{pti}(R)$ is defined to be the sum of all pressures within the region R multiplied by the duration of the applied pressures:

$$P_{pti}(R) = \sum_{t=0}^T \left[\Delta t \sum_{(x,y) \in R} V(x,y,t) \right] \quad (4)$$

In the above equation, the change in time, Δt , is defined to be the duration between sampled time points. For example, if pressures were sampled at a frequency of 200 Hz, the the duration between the sampled time points is $\Delta t = \frac{1}{200} = 0.005 \text{ s}$.

Region-Time Curve: Peak Pressure (ROI-TIME-PEAK)

The peak pressure region-time curve $P_{peak}(R, t)$ is defined to be a one-dimensional function parameterized by time. At each time point, the peak pressure region-time curve reports the maximum plantar pressure within the region, at the given time point:

$$P_{peak}(R, t) = \max_{(x,y) \in R} V(x,y,t) \quad (5)$$

Region-Time Curve: Mean Pressure (ROI-TIME-MEAN)

The mean pressure region-time curve $P_{mean}(R, t)$ is defined to be a one-dimensional function parameterized by time. At each time point, the mean pressure region-time curve reports the average plantar pressure within the region, at the given time point:

$$P_{mean}(R, t) = \frac{1}{Z(t)} \sum_{(x,y) \in R} V(x,y,t) \quad (6)$$

In the equation above, the normalization constant $Z(t)$ is defined to be the number of non-zero plantar pressures recorded in the region of interest at the given time point:

$$Z(t) = \sum_{(x,y) \in R} -\delta[V(x,y,t)] + 1 \quad (7)$$

In the above equation, δ is the Dirac delta function.

Region-Time Curve: Pressure-Time Integral (ROI-TIME-PTI)

The pressure time integral region-time curve $P_{pti}(R, t)$ is defined to be a one-dimensional function parameterized by time. At each time point, the region-time curve reports the sum of plantar pressures within the region, at the given time point, multiplied by the duration of the sampling Δt :

$$P_{pti}(R, t) = \Delta t \sum_{(x,y) \in R} V(x, y, t) \quad (8)$$

Center of Pressure Trajectory (COP)

The center of pressure trajectory $COP(t)$ is defined to be a one-dimensional function parameterized by time. At a given time point, the center of pressure is a weighted combination of pixels, where each pixel is weighted by its corresponding plantar pressure:

$$COP(t) = \frac{1}{W(t)} \sum_{(x,y)} V(x, y, t) \cdot [x, y] \quad (9)$$

In the above equation, the normalization constant $W(t)$ is equal to the sum of pressures within the frame at the given time point t :

$$W(t) = \sum_{(x,y)} V(x, y, t) \quad (10)$$

Velocity of the Center of Pressure (VOP)

The velocity of the center of pressure $VOP(t)$ is defined to be a one-dimensional function parameterized by time. At a given time point, the velocity of the center of pressure is equal to change in the center of pressure from the previous time point, divided by the duration between the sampled time points:

$$VOP(t) = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \cdot [COP(t) - COP(t - \Delta t)] \quad (11)$$

There is one exception to the equation above: when $t = 0$. For this exceptional case, we define the velocity of the center of pressure to be zero ($VOP(0) = 0$).

Peak Pressure Image (PEAK IMAGE)

The peak pressure image $P_{peak}(x, y)$ is defined to be a two-dimensional function parameterized by a pixel. Given a pixel, the peak pressure image reports the maximum pressure recorded at that spatial location, over all time points:

$$P_{peak}(x, y) = \max_t V(x, y, t) \quad (12)$$

Mean Pressure Image (MEAN IMAGE)

The mean pressure image $P_{mean}(x, y)$ is defined to be a two-dimensional function parameterized by a pixel. Given a pixel, the mean pressure image reports the average pressure recorded at that spatial location, over all time points with non-zero plantar pressures:

$$P_{mean}(x, y) = \frac{1}{Z(x, y)} \sum_{t=0}^T V(x, y, t) \quad (13)$$

In the above equation, the normalization constant $Z(x, y)$ is defined to be the number of time points at which a non-zero plantar pressure was recorded at the given pixel:

$$Z(x, y) = \sum_{t=0}^T -\delta[V(x, y, t)] + 1 \quad (14)$$

Pressure-Time Integral Image (PTI IMAGE)

The pressure-time integral image $P_{pti}(x, y)$ is defined to be a two-dimensional function parameterized by a pixel. Given a pixel, the pressure-time integral image reports the sum of the plantar pressure at that spatial location multiplied by the duration of time for which that pressure is applied:

$$P_{pti}(x, y) = \sum_{t=0}^T [\Delta t \cdot V(x, y, t)] \quad (15)$$

The change in time, Δt , is defined the same way as in equation (4) to be the duration between sampled time points.